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The Role of Government in Financing Health Services

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Abstract: This study aims to explain the role of the Central and Regional Governments in health financing. The research method used is normative research, which uses primary and secondary legal sources. The analysis was carried out qualitatively. The research findings show that the Government has a vital role in financing based on the National Social Security System (SJSN). The role of the Government has begun since the collection of funds. Furthermore, the Government, through BPJS, provides health financing payment services. Health financing is provided through capitation at Primary Health Facilities and INA-CBG at Advanced Health Facilities.

Keywords: INA-CBG, Capitation, National Social Security System, National Health Insurance, Regional Health Insurance.

Introduction

The health index is one of the most important elements in the development of a country, so the country has a health implementation system to achieve the goal of making the community healthy

(Takdir, 2018). Community participation is an absolute requirement for success in the health sector. The community's success in obtaining health cannot be separated from health efforts in funding health service facilities to realize optimal health levels for the community with maintenance, improvement, prevention, cure of disease, and health recovery approaches. (Jati & Syamsulhuda, 2009). Therefore, the government must resolve all problems regarding the implementation of health services by continuing to improve the integrated one-stop health service system so that services are professional, effective, and satisfying for the community.

The laws and regulations governing the community's right to obtain health are stated in the 1945 Constitution, Article 28 H paragraph (1): "Everyone has the right to live in physical and spiritual prosperity, to have a place to live, and to have a good and healthy living environment and has the right to obtain health services" and Article 34 paragraph (3) "The state is responsible for providing adequate health service facilities and public service facilities." In the mandate of the 1945 Constitution, the state is obliged to guarantee the right to health for all its people. So in 2004, the government formed Law Number 40 of 2004 concerning the National Social Security System (SJSN); in Article 19 paragraph (2), the purpose of establishing SJSN is stated, namely, "Health insurance is organized to ensure that participants receive health care benefits and protection in meeting basic health needs."

Health financing in Indonesia has evolved significantly in improving the community's access and quality of health services. This is reflected in the regulations and policies issued by the government to adjust policies to the community's health needs. Law Number 23 of 1992 concerning Health regulates the Community Health Care Guarantee (JPKM). The Community Health Care Guarantee (JPKMM) program regulates health financing for the underprivileged. Then it changed its name to Health Insurance (ASKES) and Health Insurance for Poor Families (Askesin), and changed its name again to Jamkesmas in 2008, which was then issued by the Minister of Health Regulation Number 903/Menkes/Per/V/2011 concerning Guidelines for the Implementation of the Community Health Insurance Program (Kementerian Kesehatan Republik Indonesia, 2011). Furthermore, *Jamkesmas* changed its name to National Health Insurance (JKN) as a health financing system based on social insurance managed by BPJS Kesehatan to provide health protection to all Indonesian people with the stipulation of "Minister of Health Regulation Number 28 of 2014 concerning Guidelines for the Implementation of National Health Insurance" (Kementerian Kesehatan Republik Indonesia, 2014).

Health financing is divided into several types: Personal-Based Financing (out of pocket), Commercial Insurance, Company Insurance, and Social Insurance. Before the realization of national health insurance, the most common health financing was personal-based financing. However, not all levels of society can feel the benefits of equal health services. Based on DJSN (2021), it is estimated that in 20230, 25% of the total population of Indonesia will be elderly and prone to degenerative diseases, which ultimately reduce productivity and various other impacts. Thus, unexpected health costs increased. Therefore, in realizing the role of the government in providing social security that is evenly distributed to all levels of society, regulations related to the implementation of social security were formed.

In realizing the objectives of social security, there needs to be a public legal entity that acts as an organizer to realize the social security system (Sulastono, 2006). Therefore, the government issued Law Number 24 of 2011 concerning the Social Security Administering Agency and formed a legal entity to realize social security throughout Indonesia. The Social Security Administering Agency is then abbreviated as BPJS. Therefore, with the issuance of Law Number 24 of 2011 concerning the establishment of the Law on the Social Security Administering Agency, it is the implementation of Law Number 40 of 2004 concerning the National Social Security System. Law Number 24 of 2011 concerning BPJS as the government's contribution in terms of health funding to realize optimal health levels for the community (Firdanus, 2015). In Law Number 17 of 2024 concerning health, health is a person's healthy state, both physically, mentally, and socially, and it is not just being free from disease that enables them to live productively. All forms of health efforts are needed to realize health. Health efforts are all forms of activities and/or a series of activities carried out in an integrated and sustainable manner to maintain and improve the health of the community in the form of promotive, preventive, curative, rehabilitative, and/or palliative by the Central Government, Regional Government, and/or the community. Health efforts cannot run without funding from the government for health service facilities. In fact, according to (Siahaan et al., 2020), health funding has an important role in the cycle of realizing a good health index by a country; poor health funding will have an impact on the delay of health workers in health services in treating patients. Drug management can be paralyzed without sufficient and sustainable funding (Siahaan et al., 2020). Based on the description above, health financing is an important component in achieving an effective health system and impacts achieving health levels.

Research Results

According to (Endra Budi Setyawan, 2017), health financing is "the amount and allocation of funds that must be provided to be used in health efforts according to the needs of individuals, groups, and communities." Furthermore, according to (the Directorate of Public Health and Nutrition, 2023), health financing is "the arrangement of financial resources that regulate the collection, allocation, and spending of health costs with the principles of efficiency, effectiveness, economy, fairness, transparency, accountability, and sustainability to improve the highest level of public health."

According to the World Health Organization (2000), health financing refers to "the function of the health system related to the collection, allocation, and mobilization of funds to meet the community's health needs, individually and collectively." In the health system, the purpose of health financing is "to provide funding, establish incentives or financing for service providers, and ensure that all individuals have access to public health services effectively." Furthermore, WHO explains that health financing refers to using financial resources to ensure that the health system can meet each person's health needs collectively and adequately (WHO, 2010).

So, it can be concluded that health financing is the management of financial resources in the health system, which includes the collection, allocation, and use of funds to meet the health needs of the community, both individual and collective (community) in order to achieve an optimal increase in the level of public health. Health financing aims to fund health development sustainably in sufficient

amounts, allocated relatively, and utilized effectively and efficiently to improve the community's health as much as possible. In implementing health financing, several elements exist, including funding sources, allocation, and utilization.

Health financing comes from “the central government, regional governments, and other legitimate sources in accordance with the provisions of laws and regulations.” The government's source of funding comes from the central government's allocation of the APBN, APBD, and Special Allocation Funds (DAK) for health, which are focused on underdeveloped, border, and island areas.

Other funding sources come from participant contributions, both individual and employer contributions. Contributions are an amount of money paid regularly by participants, employers, and/or the central government or regional government for the Health Insurance Program. The funding source also comes from participants, generally fixed contributions for informal workers and based on a percentage of income for formal workers, with a salary deduction or auto-debit mechanism. Meanwhile, the mechanism for fixed contributions is direct payment.

However, low-income groups are excluded from individual contribution funding sources. Low-income groups will be given subsidies and included in the Contribution Assistance Recipient (PBI) group, where they will receive full subsidies from the government for the poor and underprivileged. PBI Health Insurance is for the poor and underprivileged as participants in the Health Insurance Program.

The amount of contributions paid by Contribution Participants varies. PPU Participants are subject to a contribution of 5% of their monthly salary, consisting of 2% paid by the participant and 3% paid by the Employer for State Civil Apparatus (ASN). For non-ASN participants, the contribution is 5% of the salary, with a description of 4% paid by the employer and 1% paid by the participant. Meanwhile, PBPU Participants and BP Participants are subject to Rp contributions. 25,500,-/person (class III); Rp. 51,000,-/person (class II); and Rp. 80,000,-/person (class I). Next, the contribution amount for pension recipients is 5%. The revenue collection method uses a single pool system. The flow of government funds includes collecting income from households, private companies, and external sources and transferring it to government regions and health facilities. BPJS Kesehatan is the National Health Insurance (JKN) administrator, which collects contributions from the government, private companies, and households into one national pool and purchases health services from public and private providers. The flow of personal funds includes Out-of-pocket (OOP) expenditures from households and companies in public and private facilities. In Gunawan Widjaja (2018), to organize the implementation of SJSN, Law 40/2004 only states that BPJS will function as the sole institution, and Law Number 12 of 2011 does not give BPJS the authority to create or issue laws and regulations (Widjaja, 2018).

According to the Minister of Health Regulation No. 28 of 2014 concerning Guidelines for Implementing the National Health Insurance Program, the Mechanism for Payment of Participant Contributions to BPJS Kesehatan is adjusted to the membership registered with BPJS Kesehatan. The mechanism for payment of health financing to Health Facilities is differentiated based on the type of Health Facility. At Primary Health Facilities (FKTP), health financing payments are made through

capitation and non-capitation. At Advanced Health Facilities (FKTL), health financing payments are made with and outside the INA-CBG package system.

Capitation payments by BPJS Kesehatan to FKTP, such as Community Health Centers (Puskesmas), Primary Clinics, and Independent Doctor Practices, are based on the number of participants registered at FKTP according to BPJS Kesehatan data. According to Mohamed (2024) in Gunawan Widjaja (2024), primary health services are an approach targeting the entire community to effectively regulate and strengthen the national health system to bring health and welfare services closer to the community (Widjaja & Nur Mailinda, 2024). Capitation Tariff is the amount of per capita payment per month paid in advance by BPJS Kesehatan to Primary Health Facilities based on the number of registered participants without taking into account the type and number of health services provided. Capitation payments at FKTP are made by BPJS Kesehatan every month no later than the 15th of the current month.

Before the enactment of Presidential Regulation (Perpres) Number 32 of 2014 concerning the Management and Utilization of JKN Capitation Funds at FKTPs Owned by Regional Governments and the Regulation of the Minister of Health (Permenkes) Number 19 of 2014 concerning the Use of JKN Capitation Funds for Health Services and Operational Cost Support at FKTPs Owned by Regional Governments, Capitation Fund payments by BPJS to FKTPs of Regional Governments were made directly to the District/City Health Office which was then deposited into the Regional Treasury (KASDA) or directly from BPJS Kesehatan to the Regional Treasury as regional revenue. Since the enactment of PerPres Number 32 of 2014 and Permenkes Number 19 of 2014, Capitation funds have been paid directly by BPJS Kesehatan to FKTPs owned by Regional Governments.

In the payment of health service financing in FKTL, such as Hospitals using the INA CBGs system. The Indonesian-Case Based Groups Tariff, hereinafter referred to as the INA-CBGs Tariff, is the amount of claim payment by BPJS Kesehatan to Advanced Referral Health Facilities (FKTL) for service packages based on the grouping of disease diagnoses and procedures, covering all hospital resources used in both medical and non-medical services. This payment is based on submitting claims from FKRTL for both outpatient and inpatient services. FKRTL claims are paid by BPJS Kesehatan no later than 15 days after the claim files are received in full. The INA-CBGs tariff includes additional payments (top-up payments) for Special Casemix Main Groups (CMG), which consist of special procedures, special drugs, special investigations, special prostheses, subacute cases, and chronic cases. The case-mix system is a grouping of diagnoses and procedures with reference to similar/same clinical characteristics and similar/same treatment costs; grouping is done using a grouper.

Conclusions

Health financing is the management of financial resources in the health system that includes the collection, allocation, and use of funds to meet the community's health needs, both individual and collective. Sources of health financing come from the Central Government, Regional Governments, and other legitimate sources, including contributions from participants, individuals, and employers. The revenue collection mechanism uses a single pool system, with BPJS Kesehatan as the National

Health Insurance (JKN) administrator. Primary health facilities (FKTP) payments are made through capitation and non-capitation. In contrast, payments to advanced health facilities (FKTL) use the INA-CBG package system and are outside the INA-CBG package. The capitation and INA-CBG rates vary based on the type of health facility, class, and region. There are additional payments (top-up payments) for exceptional cases in the INA-CBGs system. The health financing system in Indonesia aims to ensure access to health services for all people, including low-income groups, through the Contribution Assistance Recipient (PBI) program. PBI is one form of government role in the National Social Security System (SJSN) to realize the 1945 Law article 28 H paragraph 1 and article 34 paragraph 3.

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